

Interaction of Alkyl-substituted Thiurets and Aromatic Amines : Formation of *N*-Arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamides and their Oxidation to the Related 3-Arylamino- 5-alkylamino-1, 2, 4-thiadiazoles*

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Like their aryl homologues the hydrogen halides of the alkyl-substituted thiurets react with the aromatic amines to afford the related *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamides. The structure of these has been confirmed by their preparation by the condensation of appropriate alkyl isothiocyanates with arylguanidines or by the reaction of the related *N'*-alkyl-*N*-cyanothiocarbamide with aromatic amines. The formamidothiocarbamides on oxidation undergo ring closure, forming 3-arylamino-5-alkylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles.

The interaction of hydrogen halides of aryl-substituted thiurets (I) and aromatic amines has been shown to afford *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-arylthiocarbamides (II), which when oxidised undergo ring closure to (III), the related 3,5-diarylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles or thiadiazolidines (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 151).

The above reactions have now been investigated with respect to the following :

- (i) Methylthiuret hydriodide and aniline, *p*-toluidine, and *p*-phenetidide.
- (ii) Ethylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-toluidine and *p*-phenetidide.
- (iii) Dimethylthiuret hydriodide and aniline and *p*-phenetidide.

In all cases a thiocarbamide of type (II) (where in place of Ar, the above alkyl groups were substituted) was obtained. The products in the first two cases were identified with the *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamides obtained by condensation of the appropriate arylguanidine and alkyl isothiocyanate. Thus :

(where Ar' = Ph, *p*-tolyl, and *p*-phenetyl ; R = Et and Me).

* In the previous communication (Jan. Issue, 1961, p. 44) in structure (II), double bonded S to be linked to contiguous carbon atoms instead of the N atoms as shown by mistake.

In the case of (ii), the product was also identified with the *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamides, obtained by the interaction of *N'*-dimethyl-*N*-cyanothiocarbamide and aniline or *p*-phenetidine.

(where Ar' = phenyl or *p*-phenetyl).

The above *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkyl(or dialkyl)-thiocarbamides, when oxidised with iodine, afforded in all cases the thiadiazoles or thiadiazolidines (III, where Ar is replaced by R which is Me, Et or Me₂).

EXPERIMENTAL

Interaction of Alkyl-substituted Thiuret Hydriodides and Aromatic Amines

Formation of *N*-Arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamides.—The required thiuret hydriodide (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 44) and the aromatic amine in the molecular proportion of 1:1.5 were heated on a water bath under reflux in ethanolic medium for about 30 minutes. On cooling, the separated sulphur was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to a viscous mass, which solidified on cooling. The unchanged amine and the traces of free sulphur were removed by washing with ether and CS₂. The product was desulphurizable with sodium plumbite solution as was to be expected in the case of compounds (i) to (v) below, and was found in each case identical with the expected hydriodide of the *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamide. The hydriodides could be recrystallised from hot water or chlorobenzene. The free thiocarbamide was obtained in each case by treatment of the salt with alkali and was crystallised from chlorobenzene. The picrates were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of the thiocarbamide and picric acid. The following *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamide hydriodides and the related free thiocarbamide bases were obtained.

(i) *N*-Phenylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide from methylthiuret hydriodide and aniline, m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 32.14; H, 4.05; N, 16.95; S, 9.85. C₉H₁₂N₄IS requires C, 32.14; H, 3.86; N, 16.66; S, 9.52%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 60-61°; picrate, m.p. 177°.

(ii) *N*-*p*-Tolylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide from methylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-toluidine, m.p. 156°. (Found: C, 34.20; H, 4.22; N, 16.28. C₁₀H₁₂N₄SI requires C, 34.28; H, 4.28; N, 16.0%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: N, 25.38; S, 14.32. C₁₀H₁₄N₄S requires N, 25.12; S, 14.41%). Picrate, m.p. 193°.

(iii) *N*-*p*-Phenetylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide from methylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-phenetidine, m.p. 184°. (Found: N, 14.77. C₁₁H₁₇ON₄SI requires N, 14.73%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 91-92°. (Found: C, 52.66; H, 6.42; N, 22.16; S, 13.03. C₁₁H₁₆ON₄S requires C, 52.38; H, 6.34; N, 22.22; S, 12.69%). Picrate, m.p. 134°.

(iv) *N*-*p*-Tolylformamido-*N'*-ethylthiocarbamide hydriodide from ethylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-toluidine, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 36.71; H, 4.85; N, 15.16; S, 8.99. C₁₁H₁₇N₄IS requires C, 36.26; H, 4.67; N, 15.38; S, 8.79%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 64-65°. Picrate, m.p. 148°.

(v) *N*-*p*-Phenetylformamido-*N'*-ethylthiocarbamide hydriodide from ethylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-phenetidine, m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 14.24. C₁₂H₁₉ON₄IS requires N, 14.21%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 54.26; H, 6.72; N, 21.02; S, 12.43. C₁₂H₁₈ON₄S requires C, 54.13; H, 6.76; N, 21.05; S, 12.03%). Picrate, m.p. 161°.

(vi) *N*-Phenylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide hydriodide from dimethylthiuret hydriodide and aniline, m.p. 148°. (Found : N, 15.86. $C_{10}H_{15}N_4S$ requires N, 16.0%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 106°. (Found : C, 53.63; H, 6.36; N, 25.0; S, 14.46. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S$ requires C, 54.05; H, 6.30; N, 25.22; S, 14.41%). This was identified with the product obtained in experiment (iv) from *N'*-dimethyl-*N*-cyanothiocarbamide and aniline. Picrate, m.p. 130°.

(vii) *N*-*p*-Phenetylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide hydriodide from dimethylthiuret hydriodide and *p*-phenetidine, m.p. 158°. (Found : N, 14.42. $C_{12}H_{19}ON_4S$ requires N, 14.21%). Free thiocarbamide, m.p. 94-95°. (Found : C, 54.06; H, 6.81; N, 21.02; S, 12.18. $C_{12}H_{18}ON_4S$ requires C, 54.13; H, 6.76; N, 21.05; S, 12.03%). This was identified with the product obtained in experiment (iv) from *N'*-dimethyl-*N*-cyanothiocarbamide and *p*-phenetidine.

Oxidation of *N*-Arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamides by Iodine

Formation of 3-Arylamino-5-alkylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles.—To the *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamide (about 2 g.), dissolved in ethanol (10 c.c.), aqueous iodine in KI was added gradually with stirring in slight excess. The reaction mixture was cooled and the free thiadiazole bases precipitated by basification with alkali. These were filtered, washed, and crystallised from chlorobenzene in each case. Picrates were prepared by mixing an ethanolic solution of thiadiazoles and picric acid.

(i) *3-Phenylamino-5-methylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 153°. (Found : C, 51.52; H, 4.78; N, 26.86; S, 15.21. $C_9H_{10}N_4S$ requires C, 52.42; H, 4.85; N, 27.18; S, 15.53%). Picrate, m.p. 195°.

(ii) *3-p-Tolylamino-5-methylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N-p*-tolylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 128°. (Found : C, 55.33; H, 5.38; N, 25.23; S, 15.85. $C_{10}H_{12}N_4S$ requires C, 54.54; H, 5.45; N, 25.45; S, 14.54%). Picrate, m.p. 175°.

(iii) *3-p-Phenethylamino-5-methylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N-p*-phenethylformamido-*N'*-methylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 137°. (Found : C, 52.39; H, 5.59; N, 22.33; S, 13.14. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_4S$ requires C, 52.80; H, 5.60; N, 22.40; S, 12.80%). Picrate, m.p. 167°.

(iv) *3-p-Tolylamino-5-ethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N-p*-tolylformamido-*N'*-ethylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 134°. (Found : C, 56.45; H, 6.02; N, 24.14; S, 13.53. $C_{11}H_{14}N_4S$ requires C, 56.41; H, 5.98; N, 23.93; S, 13.67%). Picrate, m.p. 210°.

(v) *3-p-Phenethylamino-5-ethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N-p*-phenethylformamido-*N'*-ethylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 144-45°. (Found : C, 54.23; H, 6.02; N, 20.98; S, 12.46. $C_{12}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires C, 54.54; H, 6.06; N, 21.21; S, 12.12%). Picrate, m.p. 172°.

(vi) *3-Phenylamino-5-dimethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 186-87°. (Found : C, 54.70; H, 5.38; N, 25.28; S, 14.75. $C_{10}H_{12}N_4S$ requires C, 54.54; H, 5.45; N, 25.45; S, 14.54%). Picrate, m.p. 191°.

(vii) *3-p-Phenethylamino-5-dimethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* by oxidation of *N-p*-phenethylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide hydriodide, m.p. 178°. (Found : C, 54.90; H, 5.76; N, 21.14; S, 12.26. $C_{12}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires C, 54.54; H, 6.06; N, 21.21; S, 12.12%). Picrate, m.p. 182°.

Condensation of Monoarylguanidines (carbonates) and Alkyl Isothiocyanates to N-Arylformamido-N'-alkylthiocarbamides and their Oxidation to the Related 3-Arylamino-5-alkylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles

The required monoarylguanidine carbonate and alkyl isothiocyanate (where aryl=phenyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-phenetyl- and alkyl=methyl- and ethyl-) in equimolecular proportions were heated in ethanolic medium under reflux for about 30 minutes. On concentration and cooling, a sticky mass was obtained in each case, which presented difficulties in crystallisation. On crystallisation from ethanol to which some hydriodic acid had been added, crystals of the expected thiocarbamide hydroiodide were obtained. Picrates were prepared from ethanolic solution. On oxidation with iodine in ethanol medium, the above obtained *N*-arylformamido-*N'*-alkylthiocarbamide hydroiodides gave the related 3-arylamino-5-alkylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazoles. The thiocarbamide hydroiodides, their picrates and the thiadiazoles obtained by their oxidation have been identified by un-depressed mixed m.p.'s with the respective products described above.

Condensation of N'-Dimethyl-N-cyanothiocarbamide with Aniline and p-Phenetidine

Formation of N-Phenylformamido- and N-p-Phenetylformamido-N'-dimethylthiocarbamides and their Oxidation to the Related Thiadiazoles.—Equimolecular quantities of *N'*-dimethyl-*N*-cyanothiocarbamide and aniline or *p*-phenetidide were heated under reflux in ethanol solution for about 30 minutes. On concentration and cooling, crystals of the expected thiocarbamide separated. Crystallisation was effected with chlorobenzene. On oxidation with iodine in ethanol the related thiadiazoles were formed :

(a) *N-Phenylformamido-N'-dimethylthiocarbamide*, m.p. 106°. (Found : C, 54.28 ; H, 6.41 ; N, 25.44 ; S, 14.77. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S$ requires C, 54.05 ; H, 6.30 ; N, 25.22 ; S, 14.41%.)

(b) *3-Phenylamino-5-dimethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* from *N*-phenylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide, m.p. 186-87°. (Found : C, 55.20 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 25.32 ; S, 14.87. $C_{10}H_{12}N_4S$ requires C, 54.54 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 25.45 ; S, 14.54%.)

(c) *N-p-Phenetylformamido-N'-dimethylthiocarbamide*, m.p. 94-95°. (Found : C, 55.15 ; H, 7.07 ; N, 21.32 ; S, 11.88. $C_{12}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires C, 54.13 ; H, 6.76 ; N, 21.05 ; S, 12.03%.)

(d) *3-p-Phenetylamino-5-dimethylamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole* from *N-p*-phenetylformamido-*N'*-dimethylthiocarbamide, m.p. 178°. (Found : C, 54.71 ; H, 6.12 ; N, 21.40 ; S, 12.36. $C_{12}H_{16}ON_4S$ requires C, 54.54 ; H, 6.06 ; N, 21.21 ; S, 12.12%.)

These thiocarbamides and thiadiazoles were found identical by un-depressed mixed m.p.'s with the corresponding products described above (*vide supra*).

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